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SCREENING AND DETECTION OF ALPHA AMYLASE INHIBITORS PRODUCED BY MARINE MICROORGANISMS BY MODIFIED TLC AND RPTLC METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Screening and detection of marine actinomycetes producing alpha amylase inhibitor was carried out by modified TLC plate method and new RPTLC plate method respectively. Out of 200 isolates only one α -amylase inhibitor producing strain was isolated from the marine sediment collected from Tamilnadu coast of Bay of Bengal. The strain showed some similarities with strain *Streptomyces lateritius* like antibiotic production and similar sporophore formation. However, more differences were observed with respect to carbon sources utilization, hence it was designated as *Streptomyces lateritius* var TP4/6. This paper involves development of modified TLC and RPTLC method for screening of proteinaceous amylase inhibitors. These methods are more reliable than existing methods like starch plate, starch agar plate and TLC plate method for primary screening of alpha amylase inhibitors. Our strain TP4/6 characteristics were compared with the existed strain *Streptomyces lateritius* and concluded that it is a variety of the existed one. This was the first report on screening and detection of proteinaceous amylase inhibitor using these methods.

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INTRODUCTION

The main aim of the study is to overcome the drawbacks of the previous methods and to develop new methods to screen and detect alpha amylase inhibitors from microorganisms. An alpha amylase is an enzyme that breaks down starch into sugar [1, 2]. Alpha amylase is present in human saliva, where it begins the chemical process of digestion. It is one of the enzymes important in controlling blood sugar levels in the body. Inhibiting α -amylase could be a beneficial treatment for insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, obesity and hyperlipidemia. Amylase inhibitors are useful tools for the determination of activities of amylase isozyme [3] and purification of amylases. To date; most amylase inhibitors were isolated from plants and microorganisms using different screening techniques. A number of rapid methods were employed to screen α -amylase inhibitors producing microorganisms like Starch plate method [4], Starch agar plate method [5] and TLC plate method [6]. To overcome the shortcomings of these methods, we developed a modified TLC plate method (modified thin-layer chromatography) by using starch as substrate, agar as solidifying agent and amylase enzyme soaked Whatman paper, to screen the effective α -amylase inhibitor producing microorganisms or plant extracts in a rapid, and accurate manner. Screening of 200 marine microorganisms resulted in isolation of one actinomycete strain with the ability to secrete potent alpha amylase inhibitor. This paper describes the screening of amylase inhibitor producing microorganisms using modified TLC plate method. Previously discussed methods are used only for screening only where as this RPTLC method is the better method used to detect the activity of proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitor and taxonomical characterization of the strain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the present investigation we utilized 200 actinomycete isolates which were isolated by earlier workers in our laboratory. The isolates were maintained properly by sub culturing using starch casein agar, yeast extract and malt extract agar (ISP-2).

Importance of the study:

Now a day, Diabetes mellitus is commonly prevailing disorder among the population. By the discovery of new synthetic drug molecules we can control it, but they are having severe side effects, in order to minimize those effects we can go for naturally available molecules with minimum side effects. For example plant alpha amylase inhibitors from wheat and white kidney bean and microbial alpha amylase inhibitors like Tendamistat from *Streptomyces tendae* plays an important role in controlling blood glucose levels of diabetic people. The main objective of our study is to screen and detect novel water soluble and proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitors from different sources.

Modified TLC plate method for screening of alpha amylase inhibitor producing organisms:

Samples of broth containing the inhibitor were spotted on pre coated TLC plate (diameter 4mm); and dried. Sterilized agar containing 1.6% starch solution was poured in a sterile Petri dish and allowed to solidify. Human salivary α -amylase (1:99 dilution-using Tris HCl buffer) in 0.1 mol/L Tris HCl buffer pH 7.0) was impregnated onto a paper. Inhibitor spotted TLC plate was superimposed on the agar layer and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C, the plate was removed and the paper loaded with alpha amylase was overlaid on the substrate agar layer and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C. Aqueous iodine solution was poured on the surface after paper was peeled off. Excess iodine was removed by rinsing with water. A purple ring will appear around a sample spot that contained inhibitor.

Fermentation:

Alpha amylase inhibitor production of the selected strain TP4/6 was carried out by fermentation in shake flask on rotary shaker at 120 rpm and 37°C in a medium containing 0.6% peptone (sigma), 0.1% yeast extract (sigma), 1.0% soluble starch, pH 7.0, 25% distilled water for three days. The mycelium was removed by centrifugation (10000 rpm for 15 minutes) and the supernatant was assayed for amylase inhibitor activity by modified blue value method [7].

RPTLC (Reverse phase thin layer chromatography) method:

Our compound being a water soluble protein (tested with Ninhydrin solution), we preferred the usage of RPTLC plates for detection of the active compound. Proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitor was purified by Sephadex LH-20 gel chromatography. Activity of Proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitor was detected by a new RPTLC method. Purified inhibitor sample was loaded on (Reverse phase thin layer chromatography) RPTLC plate and the plate was transferred to previously prepared developing tank containing solvent system tris buffer pH 7.0, later the activity of purified inhibitor spot on the RPTLC plate was detected by superimposing the RPTLC plate on starch containing agar plate and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C, the plate was removed and the alpha amylase loaded paper was overlaid on the substrate agar layer and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C. Aqueous iodine solution was poured on the surface after paper was peeled off. Excess iodine was removed by rinsing with water. The presence of inhibitor can easily identify on the plate where blue color portion was formed.

Identification of organism:

To furnish reliable description of authentic, extant culture of *Streptomyces*; the criteria lay down by the International Streptomyces Project [8] (ISP) Waksman were adopted. Mycelial morphology was performed by light microscopy and Scanning electron microscopy. The cell wall composition of the isolate was carried out by the method of Lechevalier and Lechevalier [9].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the above experiments, it was indicated that we can able to easily screen and detect the presence of alpha amylase inhibitors in the natural extracts. The experiment only describes screening and to detect the activity of the microbial extracts, it's not about rate of inhibition alpha amylase and comparison of with a known compound.

Fig1: shows the action of extracted alpha amylase inhibitor on starch layer- modified TLC plate method.

The purple colored portion in Fig:1 .indicates that alpha amylase was unable to hydrolyze starch due to the presence of added alpha amylase inhibitor

Fig2: Detection of purified alpha amylase inhibitors by RPTLC method.

Proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitors are purified by ammonium sulphate precipitation followed by Sephadex LH-20 gel chromatography. Blue colored spot on the agar plate indicates inhibition of alpha amylase by purified amylase inhibitor. In TLC method (Butanol: acetic acid: water 4:1:5) the sample spot remained at the origin itself at the end of the run. By addition of iodine solution, blue color spot was developed and indicated the presence and nature of the inhibitor which was depicted in Fig:2. This observation gave us a clue to develop RPTLC method. Proteinaceous amylase inhibitors are polar in nature, so we developed this method for detection of amylase inhibitors. From the origin the sample spot migrated to the solvent front in presence of Tris HCl buffer. This was the best method to detect the presence of proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitors and nature of the inhibitor in the sample.

Table: 1 Cultural characteristic of *Streptomyces lateritius* and isolate-TP4/6.

Cultural characteristic of <i>Streptomyces lateritius</i> and isolate-TP4/6		
Medium	Cultural characteristics of <i>Streptomyces lateritius</i>	Cultural characteristics of TP4/6
Yeast extract-malt extract agar(ISP-2)	G : moderate AM: poorly developed and red color R : light brownish gray SP : none	G : Abundant AM: Light gray R : light brownish gray SP : none
Oat meal agar (ISP-3)	G : moderate AM: poorly developed and red color R : gray yellow SP : blue to violet	G : moderate AM: cream R : light cream SP : none
Inorganic salts starch agar (ISP-4)	G : Abundant AM: red color R : grayish yellow SP : blue to violet	G : Abundant AM: light gray R : gray SP : none
Glycerol-asparagine agar (ISP-5)	G : poor AM: no aerial mycelium R : grayish yellow	G : moderate AM: light gray R : light gray

Starch casein agar	SP : blue to violet	SP : none
	G : abundant	G : abundant
	AM: gray	AM: gray
	R : light gray	R : light gray
	SP : blue to violet	SP : none
G: growth AM: aerial mycelium R: reverse color SP: soluble pigment		

Our isolate TP4/6 and *Streptomyces lateritius* have the following dissimilarities:

- The results table:1 indicated that the cultural characteristics of both standard strain and our isolate TP4/6. TP4/6 exhibited good growth on L-arabinose, D-glucose, D-mannitol, raffinose, Doubtful growth on sucrose and no growth on D-xylose, L-rhamnose, meso-inositol, and D-fructose.
- It shows good growth on inorganic salts starch agar (ISP-4) and yeast extract and malt extract agar (ISP-2), moderate growth on Glycerol-asparagine agar (ISP-5) and poor growth on Oat meal agar (ISP-3)
- Streptomyces lateritius* exhibited good growth on L-arabinose, D-glucose, D-xylose, L-rhamnose and D-fructose, Doubtful growth on meso-inositol, no growth on Sucrose, mannitol and raffinose.
- Our isolate TP4/6 shows abundant growth on inorganic salts starch agar (ISP-4) and starch casein agar, poor growth on Glycerol-asparagine agar (ISP-5) and moderate growth on Oat meal agar (ISP-3) and Yeast extract and malt extract agar (ISP-2).

Table: 2 physiological and biochemical properties of isolate TP4/6.

S.No	Reaction	Response	Result
1	Gram staining	Blue color	Positive
2	Spore staining	No color	Negative
3	Growth at 12 ^o C	Growth was observed	Positive
4	Growth at 25 ^o C	Growth was observed	Positive
5	Growth at 37 ^o C	Growth was observed	Positive
6	Growth at 42 ^o C	Growth was observed	Positive
7	Growth at pH 5.2	Growth was observed	Positive
8	Growth at pH 8.0	Growth was observed	Positive
9	Growth at pH 9.0	Growth was observed	Positive
10	Growth at pH 10.0	Growth was observed	Positive
11	Growth on NaCl 2%	Growth was observed	Positive
12	Growth on NaCl 5%	Growth was observed	Positive
13	Growth on NaCl 7%	No growth	Negative
14	Growth on NaCl 10%	No growth	Negative
15	Melanin reaction on ISP-1 ISP-6 ISP-7	No brown coloration was observed on all media	Negative
16	Starch hydrolysis	Growth zone = 12mm Hydrolyzed zone =27mm	Positive
17	Casein hydrolysis	No hydrolyzed zone was observed	Negative
18	Gelatin liquefaction	No hydrolyzed zone was observed	Negative
20	H ₂ S production	No brown color	Negative
21	Nitrate reduction	Brown color	Positive
22	Tyrosine reaction	No brown color	Negative
23	Antibiotic production	Zone inhibition observed	Positive

The results of table: 2 indicated that the biochemical tests, staining and growth at different temperature, pH and NaCl concentrations. The isolate TP4/6 grew in the temperature range of 20-45^oC, NaCl concentration range of 2-5%. Grams staining reaction indicated that the isolate belongs to gram positive organism, able to grow at pH 10 and at concentration of NaCl-5% only. Our isolate TP4/6 can able produce antibiotic like the standard isolate *Streptomyces lateritius*. *Streptomyces lateritius* produces naphthoquinone type antibiotic called granaticin^[10], which is a broad spectrum antibiotic.

Fig3: Scanning electron micrograph of the isolate TP4/6.

The morphological characteristic of isolate TP4/6 having aerial mycelium containing hooks with open loops. On maturity, it divided and formed spiral spore chains. Each spore chain held about 10 to 20 spores. The size of each elliptical spore was about 1.0 to 1.1 μm . The surface of the spore was smooth, no sclerotic granules, sporangia or zoospores were observed in Fig 3. Chemical analysis of cell wall and whole cell sugar pattern of isolate TP4/6 showed that it contained L-L Diaminopimelic acid, glycine and no sugars.

Spore chain morphology of *Streptomyces lateritius*:

The sporophores occurred as *Retinaculia aperti*, but the spore chains representative of section RF are also common. Mature spore chains generally consists of 10 to 50 spores per chain; longer chains are observed some times. The spore surface is warty.

DISCUSSION

The existing TLC plate method was modified for screening of alpha amylase inhibitor producing microorganisms. In the modified TLC plate, there is no need to add hot agar containing starch suspension on to the TLC plate containing salivary alpha amylase. Hot starch suspension may affect the activity of heat labile amylase inhibitors. In case of starch agar plate method, there may be a chance of contamination by stab inoculating the isolates on the starch agar containing plate. RPTLC method was the new method developed to detect the activity of proteinaceous amylase inhibitors followed by reverse phase thin layer chromatography. We can further separate the active fractions of amylase inhibitors based on their Rf values by this method. Our isolate and *S.lateritius* have major dissimilarities in carbon utilization pattern and growth characteristics on various ISP media. In view of large number of differences, our isolate TP4/6 can be considered as a new variant of *Streptomyces lateritius*. Hence it is designated as *Streptomyces lateritius* var. TP4/6. The isolate was identified by IMTECH Chandigarh with accession number MTCC 10474.

CONCLUSION

The modified TLC plate and new RPTLC plate methods developed were effective for the screening and detection of proteinaceous and water soluble alpha amylase inhibitors. RPTLC plate method was the superior and precise method for detection of purified amylase inhibitors. Our methodology demonstrated that it is possible to separate active fractions of proteinaceous alpha amylase inhibitors based on their Rf values also.

Future research

By using these methods we can screen and detect number of alpha amylase inhibitors from microorganisms and plants also.

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Abbreviations:

TLC, RPTLC, IMTECH, NaCl, ISP, AM, G, R and SP

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